

RELATIONSHIPS AT RISK: THE EXPLORATION AND CONFIRMATION OF CUSTOMER DETACHMENT AND ITS DRIVERS

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Abstract

The importance of relational bonds in building and maintaining long-term customer relationships is widely acknowledged. The threats that weaken these relational bonds and endanger relationship continuation, such as detachment, are however, largely ignored in extant literature. Detachment studies, particularly within the field of marketing, are rather scarce and focus predominantly on customers detachment from a brand without considering the interpersonal relationship with an employee. To address this gap, this paper strives to conceptualise the concept of customer detachment within customer-wealth manager relationships and determine the constructs that drive it. A quantitative cross-sectional research design was implemented, collecting 536 useable online questionnaires via non-probability convenience and quota sampling methods. Exploratory structural equation modelling (ESEM) was used to model the collected data. With the exception of customer alienation, the results revealed that disaffection, disillusionment, dissatisfaction and negative emotions were significantly related to customer detachment. In conclusion, efforts to counteract detachment will play a significant role in maintaining relationships, including interpersonal relationships between customers and wealth managers. Both academics and practitioners should focus on disaffection, disillusionment, dissatisfaction, and negative emotions, as these constructs could influence the occurrence and level of detachment among their customers.

Keywords: Alienation, Customer Detachment, Disaffection, Disillusionment, Dissatisfaction, Negative Emotions

Declaration of interest

The are no conflicts of interest to be declared by the authors. All authors involved in the study have both reviewed and agreed with the contents of the manuscript and further maintain that there is no financial interest to report. We (the authors) certify that the submission's content is both original and is not under review at any other publication institution.

1 INTRODUCTION

Various marketing researchers agree that the essence of any successful and profitable customer-organisational relationship revolves around the bond

forged between them as it lays the foundation for both relationship longevity and organisational success (Spies, Eckardt, & De Beer, 2022; Moussa & Touzani, 2017). Customer attachment, which several studies have addressed over the years, is widely accepted as

being a key component of building successful customer-organisational relationships as it promotes the development of strong customer relational bonds that, in turn, foster high levels of customer satisfaction, trust, commitment, loyalty, and retention (Spies et al., 2022). While attachment has been adequately reviewed in extant literature, little to no research has addressed its equally important counterpart, detachment. Primarily a psychology concept, detachment can be defined as an individual's psychological state of distance concerning an offending attachment figure resulting from a weakening or dissolution of the affective bond between them (Eckardt & Spies, 2023; Mai & Conti, 2008). The loss of an affective bond can put strain on the individual's relationship with the offending attachment figure resulting in a desire to distance themselves from the relationship or even terminate it altogether (Perrin-Martinenq, 2004). Considering detachment's deleterious effects on relational bonds, the need to review the concept within a business relationship setting becomes evident.

A thorough literature review reveals that despite the negative consequences detachment may hold for customer relationships, only a handful of studies have addressed the concept within a marketing context. These studies include brand detachment (Hemetsberger, Kittinger-Rosanelli, & Friedmann, 2009; Mai & Conti, 2008; Perrin-Martinenq, 2004), store detachment (Borghini, Sherry, & Joy, 2020) and fashion/design detachment (Mellander & McIntyre, 2021; Thornquist, 2017). While each of these studies addresses various aspects of detachment, none touch on how it influences dyadic human interpersonal relationships such as those between a customer and employee. Eckardt and Spies (2023) also highlight this gap by stating that no insight is available on the role of detachment, specifically within a customer-employee relationship, restricting marketers and researchers current understanding of the detachment concept. Utilizing a systematized literature review these authors bridged the gap by suggesting how the detachment concept can be extended into customer-employee relationships. Their thorough literature review also revealed possible factors that could influence customer detachment, providing a better understanding of the concept. Whilst their literature study did provide a sound foundation for detachment to potentially be extended to customer-employee relationships together

with factors that could drive it, none of their suggestions were empirically tested. Building upon the work of Eckardt and Spies (2023), this study aims to empirically investigate the role of detachment specifically in customer-employee relationships by identifying the factors that drive it. The examination of customers' detachment from an employee (in this case, wealth manager) and the factors that drive it will not only theoretically and empirically clarify and explicate the role of detachment in customer-wealth manager relationships, but also contribute to the detachment research stream in marketing, which may encourage future research on the topic.

Relying on studies from psychology with an interpersonal relationship focus and the research conducted by Eckardt and Spies (2023), this study identified dissatisfaction, negative emotions, disaffection, disillusionment, and alienation as factors that could affect customer detachment. While empirical evidence linking dissatisfaction (Ali, Attiq, & Talib, 2020) and negative emotions (Lu, Lu, & Wang, 2012) towards detachment can be found, the remaining proposed drivers of disaffection, disillusionment, and alienation, are supported solely by marketing and psychology literature. By empirically testing these new and existing drivers, this study makes an original contribution to the body of knowledge in understanding customer detachment.

While the importance and contribution of studying customer detachment in building relationships are evident, no research has yet, to the best of the researcher's knowledge, examined customer detachment in the South African wealth management industry. Thus, gaining insight into customers' detachment could guide wealth managers in their efforts to build successful customer relationships within emerging markets such as South Africa. Wealth managers will also be able to use the results of this research study to create preventative and reconciliatory customer detachment strategies allowing them to ensure enduring and profitable customer relationships. Finally, by examining and confirming the hypothesised drivers of customer detachment this study will not only empirically explain the role of customer detachment in customer-wealth management relationships but also contribute to the attachment, detachment and relationship marketing research stream, which may encourage future research on the topic.

2 LITERATURE OVERVIEW

2.1 Detachment

Detachment is commonly defined as the process in which an individual distances themselves from an attachment figure due to the gradual weakening of the bond between them (Mai & Conti, 2008; Moon & Yang, 2015). One of the earliest references to detachment was made by attachment theorist Bowlby (1969), who observed that children, when separated from their mother, would display detachment-like behaviours while she was away and upon her return. Bowlby viewed this behaviour as a sign of recovery, as once the child had detached, they no longer rejected any comfort and assistance offered by strangers but rather accepted it (Johnson, 2019). Since Bowlby's identification of detachment, several other studies within the field of psychology have expanded upon the concept within relational contexts (Borghini et al., 2020; Fuhrman & Holmbeck, 1995; Marlowe, Hodgson, Lamson, 2010; Pace & Zappulla, 2013; Reibstein & reibstein, 1998; Saccardo & Calvo, 2020).

One of these contexts includes an adolescent's progression towards autonomy, also referred to as his/her journey towards gaining independence or the ability to self-regulate and govern (Ryan & Lynch, 1989; Ryan, Deci, & Vansteenkiste, 2016). During this journey, detachment can occur if the adolescent is exposed to family settings characterised by a lack of support or acceptance and negative or conflictive relationships. In instances of negative family functioning such as these, detachment will generally manifest as feelings of mistrust towards, and decreased desire to rely upon the support and guidance of the offending attachment figure (Eckardt & Spies, 2023; Pace & Zappulla, 2013). Similarly, within the sphere of adult romantic relations, affective or emotional detachment can occur due to an unsatisfactory relationship (Hadden, Rodriguez, Knee, DiBello, & Baker, 2016; Katz & Woodin, 2002). Despite the individual's dissatisfaction with the relationship, he/she does not usually experience any elevated negative affect but rather a decrease in both positive and negative affective states, which in turn can result in either or both partners leading separate lives behaviourally and emotionally (Mai & Conti, 2008; Perrin-Martinenq, 2004; Pokorska, 2016).

The concept of detachment has also been addressed to a lesser extent within the field of marketing (Borghini et al., 2020; Mellander & McIntyre, 2021), mainly focusing on customer's detachment from a brand (Mai & Conti, 2008; Perrin-Martinenq, 2004). Existing research reveals that the detachment process is generally triggered by negative events or outcomes that severely disappoint the customer, causing them to begin doubting their previously held perceptions of the brand it is related to (Evanschitzky et al., 2020; Hemetsberger et al., 2009; Perrin-Martinenq, 2004). Eckardt and Spies (2023) and Moon and Yang (2015) posit that once the process has begun, the affective or relational bond between the customer and the brand will begin to deteriorate. Subsequently, the customer will begin distancing him-/herself from the relationship by reducing the extent to which they purchase the organisation's offerings and interact with them. According to Perrin-Martinenq (2004), in addition to distancing and reduced patronage, customers who become detached may find themselves thinking less about the brand and may also be motivated to terminate the relationship altogether should it continue to deteriorate.

2.2 The potential for detachment in customer-employee relationships

While detachment has been addressed in interpersonal, relational and even brand contexts (Hadden et al., 2016; Holmes, 1982; Mai & Conti, 2008; Marlowe et al., 2010; Perrin-Martinenq, 2004), it has yet to be tested within a customer-employee setting. However, considering the information discussed above from both the fields of psychology and marketing, it is possible to surmise how customer detachment may occur. First, an initial trigger event, such as service or product failures directly related to an offending attachment figure, would cause customers to experience dissatisfaction and negative emotions (Hemetsberger et al., 2009; Vidal, Paché, & Fenneteau, 2016). Should this dissatisfaction be left unaddressed or consistently recur, customers will then begin to doubt the previous positive perceptions he/she had towards the reliability or even competency of the offending attachment figure. Once these doubts are established, customers will likely begin distancing themselves from the relationship

and become increasingly reluctant to rely on the offending figure's support or purchase their offerings (Mai & Conti, 2008). These outcomes, combined with any viable or attractive alternatives, may also lead customers to terminate their relationship with the offending figure altogether and even switch to a competitor (Perrin-Martinenq, 2004).

2.3 Relationship disaffection

Relationship disaffection is commonly defined as a gradual loss of emotional attachments that result in a decline in caring, emotional estrangement and an increased sense of apathy and indifference toward a relational partner (Abbasi, Drouin, McDaniel, & Dibble, 2019). According to Asfajir and Ramezani (2017) and Evanschitzky et al. (2020), disaffection does not occur instantaneously but rather results from a process where disappointments, dissatisfaction, and unresolved conflicts culminate in an individual losing their sense of affection for the relationship. According to Kersten (1990) the disaffection process consists of three phases throughout which individuals in the relationship undergo several emotional and behavioural changes. During the first phase, individuals will generally experience a sense of discontentedness or feelings of being unfulfilled. As a result, issues and grievances will generally become more apparent between individuals paving way for the further disaffection (Evanschitzky, 2020; Kersten, 1990). The second stage is characterised by the gradual loss of feelings such as love and affection followed by an increase of negativity or apathy between partners. At this point in the relationship individuals will start to focus more on each other's shortcomings in turn leading to a diminished sense of intimacy and connection between them (Kersten, 1990; Mohammadi & Mohammadian, 2018). In the final stage of the disaffection process the emotional ties that once bonded the individuals together will have weakened to such an extent that both partners will no longer display any interest in further maintaining the relationship (Evanschitzky, 2020; Mohammadi & Mohammadian, 2018). In line with the information discussed above, disaffection constitutes the loss of emotional ties or bonds that form a part of the detachment process as the loss of these positive affective states are what enable or even

drive individuals to ultimately sever the bond that exists between them and distance themselves from the relationship (Eckardt, 2023).

Studies by Abbasi et al. (2019), Evanschitzky et al. (2020) and Liceaga (2013) offer support for the previous statement by revealing that disaffection will generally motivate individuals to separate and distance themselves both emotionally and cognitively from the source of their previous affections. In line with this information, studies by Eckardt and Spies (2023), Mai and Conti (2008) and Perrin-Martinenq (2004) suggest that disaffection could also be linked to detachment not only within a romantic relationship setting but also within a customer-employee context. The rationale supporting this argument is that the detachment process, once triggered by various negative events or outcomes, will motivate customers to distance themselves from the offending source or attachment figure resulting in a reduced sense of affection and/or desire to maintain the relationship. Taking this information into account, this study proposes the following hypothesis:

H1: Relationship disaffection will have a significant effect on respondents' detachment from their wealth manager.

2.4 Customer disillusionment

According to Maher, Igou, and Van Tilburg (2020) disillusionment can be defined as being defeated in either or both expectation and hope. In context of interpersonal relationships disillusionment represents the de-idealisation of one's romantic partner during which their flaws and the potential limitations of the relationship become apparent (Niehuis, Reifman, & Lee, 2015). While not necessarily detrimental in nature, disillusionment can have a negative impact on relationships should it remain un-addressed or if the de-idealisation itself is profound (Kersten, 1990). In instances where the disillusionment cannot be addressed and dissatisfaction with the relationship persists, individuals will gradually become disaffected and ultimately detached (Evanschitzky et al., 2020; Niehuis et al., 2015). Evanschitzky et al. (2020) add that unmet expectations constitute a powerful element of disillusionment. These authors explain that consistent

disappointments over time lead to significant levels of dissatisfaction which drive individuals to re-evaluate the costs and benefits of the relationship.

Within a marketing context, unmet customer expectations will also lay the foundation for their eventual disillusionment, as each time an organisation fails to meet their expectations (i.e., negative disconfirmation), the customer becomes increasingly dissatisfied (Supioni, 2015). Over time, the culmination of this dissatisfaction leads the customer to re-evaluate and, consequently, form a de-idealised perception of his/her relationship with the organisation, preventing continued disappointment (Evanschitzky et al., 2020; Pervan & Martin, 2012). Pervan and Martin (2012) and Supioni (2015) maintain that once a customer is disillusioned, he/she will begin to distance themselves from the relationship with the organisation by reducing patronage and even exposure to them. Similarly, when an affective bond that exists between the customer and the organisation deteriorates due to dissatisfaction, he/she may decide to distance themselves from the relationship by reducing the extent to which they purchase the organisation's offerings and interact with them (Eckardt & Spies, 2023; Moon & Yang, 2015). According to Perrin-Martin (2004) and Rabbanee (2012), it is the deterioration of these affective bonds or ties between a customer and a brand essentially contributes to the customer's eventual state of detachment. Thus, taking the information discussed above into consideration, this study proposes the following hypothesis:

H2: Disillusionment will have a significant effect on respondents' detachment from their wealth manager.

2.5 Customer dissatisfaction

Customer dissatisfaction can be defined as the affective state experienced by a customer when he/she experiences a product or service failure (Fornell & Wernerfelt, 1987; Kim, Kim, & Heo, 2019). Based on literature from the field of psychology, satisfaction generally correlates negatively with detachment (Pace & Zappulla, 2013). The reason for this negative correlation is that within various forms of interpersonal relationships, when an individual's attachment figure is consistently unable to satisfy their needs, they will begin to re-evaluate the benefits of

maintaining the current relationship. Should the costs of maintaining the relationship, whether physical or emotional, outweigh the benefits the individual will become increasingly inclined to detach from the offending figure (Eckardt & Spies, 2023; Evanschitzky et al., 2020; Hadden et al., 2016). Similarly, being unable to satisfy a customer's needs and failing to provide consistent support can cause them to detach (Eckardt & Spies, 2023). Eckardt and Spies (2023) explain that when a customer loses confidence in both the bond they share with the offending attachment figure and the figure's ability to meet their needs, it will increase their likelihood of detaching as means to cope with the disappointment. Taking the information provided above into account, the following hypothesis is proposed for this study:

H3: Customer dissatisfaction will have a significant effect on respondents' detachment from their wealth manager.

2.6 Customer alienation

In accordance with literature from the field of social psychology, alienation can be viewed as a sense of exclusion felt by an individual due to a subjective state of mind driven by his/her expectations and values (Yener, 2014). Additionally, the term alienation can also be associated with an individual's sense of separation or estrangement from other individuals, a country and various entities or institutions (Krishnan, 2008). Within a marketing context, alienation refers to a customer's lack of identification with and feelings of separation from the various norms and values that characterise marketplace practices, interactions and relationships (Junaid, Hou, & Hussain, 2019; Mady, 2011). There are several emotions that an alienated customer may experience which can include but is not limited to powerlessness, normlessness and isolation (Eckardt, 2023). Powerlessness is characterised by a customer's belief that their actions will not be enough to obtain the outcomes or benefits they seek either in the marketplace or with an organization and its employees (Ortiz, Chih, & Tsai, 2018; Yener, 2014). Normlessness occurs when established social norms fail to regulate appropriate behaviour, causing customers to suspect that organizations or their staff might act unethically or unjustly to achieve their own objectives

(Bai et al., 2019; Mady, 2011; Ortiz et al., 2018). Isolation denotes a customer's feelings of disenchantment or separation from the marketing community and its institutions, practices, and relationships (Mady, 2011; Ortiz et al., 2018; Yener, 2014).

Burns (2010) and Yener (2014) maintain that when a customer experiences feelings of alienation such as those described above it can affect their behaviour in a variety of ways including a desire to distance themselves from institutions, social structures and by extension, relationships from which he/she may feel alienated. As distancing oneself from an offending source or attachment figure is also consistent with information pertaining to detachment in both the field of psychology (Bickelhaupt, Lohman, & Neppel, 2021; Denckla & Bornstein, 2015) and marketing (Mai & Conti, 2008; Perrin-Martinenq, 2004) the following can be hypothesised:

H4: Customer alienation will have a significant effect on respondents' detachment from their wealth manager.

2.7 Negative emotions

According to Ali et al. (2020), Charsetad, Vazifehdoost, and Nikoomaram (2016) and, Harmeling, Magnusson, and Singh (2015), when customers are

subject to events that dissatisfy him/her, such as service failures, it can induce a negative emotional response. To come to terms with these negative emotions, customers will likely adopt one of several coping strategies to reduce the effect of the resulting dissonance (Ali et al., 2020). One of these strategies can include customers distancing themselves from the source of his/her distress (i.e., the offending attachment figure) to mitigate or circumvent the potentially harmful outcomes thereof (Chen & Pham, 2019; Jung & Park, 2018). This form of emotion-based coping, also known as psychological distancing, essentially allows the customer to deal with his/her negative feelings by detaching themselves from the source of their distress (Lu et al., 2012). A study conducted by Eckardt and Spies (2023) supports the arguments above and adds that within a marketing context customers could also detach as a means to cope with negative situations or emotional distress. Therefore, this study proposes the following hypothesis:

H5: Negative emotions will have a significant effect on respondents' detachment from their wealth manager.

Figure 1 provides a visual representation of the customer detachment model proposed by this study.

Figure 1: A conceptual model of the drivers of customer detachment

Source: Author's own depiction

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research design, population, sampling and data collection

This study made use of a cross-sectional, quantitative research design to collect data. This research design was chosen to adhere to budgetary and time constraints whilst maintaining the reliability necessary to examine and establish the customer detachment concept and its proposed drivers. The research participants selected for this study included South Africans who use wealth management services and had distanced themselves from their wealth manager due to becoming detached. However, as various rules and regulations prevent wealth managers from disclosing personal details about their customers, and as a complete list of South African wealth management customers was not freely available, a sample frame could not be constructed.

Thus, this study was required to utilise a combination of non-probability sampling techniques, namely online convenience sampling in the form of computer-administered surveys and quota sampling, to gather data. While online convenience sampling was chosen based on travel and social distancing restrictions at the time of data collection, quota sampling was included to ensure a relatively even inclusion of respondents from different gender groups. In line with these sampling methods, a link to the study's questionnaire was posted on social media platforms such as Facebook and LinkedIn, along with a short message that requested and encouraged members of various community groups to participate in the study. According to Malhotra (2015), a minimum of 400 responses would be sufficient for statistical analysis purposes. However, upon completion of the data collection period, a total of 536 usable responses were obtained.

3.2 Measurement instrument

A structured questionnaire comprising of multi-item scales was used as the measurement instrument for this research study. The questionnaire included an introductory/preamble section that explained the study's purpose and screening questions that ensured only respondents who had distanced themselves from their wealth manager

due to becoming detached were able to participate in the study. The next set of questions measured various demographic variables associated with respondents who participated in the study before progressing to the measurement of the study's proposed factors: customer detachment, disaffection, disillusionment, dissatisfaction, alienation, and negative emotions. These proposed factors were all measured using closed-ended questions combined with a five-point Likert-scale response format. Using this format, participants could indicate their agreement to a particular statement on a scale of 1 to 5; 1 indicating that they "strongly disagreed", and 5 that they "strongly agreed". To the best of the researcher's knowledge, prior to this study, no scales had yet been developed for customer disaffection and disillusionment in the field of marketing; thus, scales were adapted from studies based in psychology, namely, Kayser (1996) and Pervan and Martin (2012) respectively. However, valid and reliable measurement scales for dissatisfaction (Brady & Robertson, 2001; Dagger & O'Brien, 2010), alienation (Akbari, Abdolvand, & Ghaffari, 2016), negative emotions (Koenig-Lewis & Palmer, 2014) and detachment (Mai & Conti, 2008; Perrin-Martinenq, 2004) could be found in extant marketing literature and were each adapted accordingly.

3.3 Data analysis

The data collected for this study was analysed using two statistical programmes. The first program IBM SPSS (version 27) was used to calculate descriptive statistics and Cronbach's alpha coefficients. The second program Mplus version 8.3. was used to assess the validity and reliability of the measurement scales via exploratory structural equation modelling (ESEM) and to test the relationships between respondents' disaffection, disillusionment, dissatisfaction, alienation, negative emotions, and detachment. Several fit indices namely, Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR), The Tucker Lewis Index (TLI) and Comparative Fit Indexes (CFI) were also calculated and consulted in tandem with the ESEM to confirm the model fit. RMSEA is used as an absolute measure of fit that determines the degree to which the overall and structural models predict the ob-

served covariance (Kenny, Kaniskan, & McCoach, 2015; O’Rourke & Hatcher, 2013), whereas the SRMR analyses the average discrepancy between observable correlations in the input matrix and the correlations predicted by the model (Brown, 2015; Malhotra, Nunan, & Birks, 2017). According to Shi, Lee, and Maydeu-Olivares (2019) and Cho, Hwang, Sarstedt, and Ringle (2020), RMSEA values of ≤ 0.10 and SRMR of values ≤ 0.08 can be considered acceptable. Subsequently, the TLI compares the χ^2 indices for the model tested to a null model, which serves to prove that all measured variables are uncorrelated (Bentler, 1990). Similarly, the CFI compares the sample covariance matrix with the null model, which assumes that all latent variables are uncorrelated (Hooper, Coughlan, & Mullen, 2008). According to Hu and Bentler (1999), if both the TLI and CFI values are ≥ 0.95 , they are considered acceptable.

For the purposes of this study, the data was treated as ordered categorical and therefore, weighted least squares (mean- and variance-adjusted) rather than maximum likelihood estimation was used as a means to estimate the parameters of the proposed model (Marsh, Morin, Parker, & Kaur, 2014). To determine the extent to which the six factors within the proposed detachment model correlate with one another (i.e., detachment, disaffection, disillusionment, dissatisfaction, alienation and negative emotions) factor correlations were calculated. For the factor correlations, values of $r \geq 0.30$ were considered to have a medium practical effect, whereas, values of $r \geq 0.50$ were viewed as having a large practical effect (Cohen, 1988).

4 RESULTS

4.1 Sample profile

Based on the data recorded, the majority of participants had been using their wealth manager’s services for between 1 to 5 years (40.5%), with insurance (53.9%) being the most popular wealth management service provided. The gender of respondents was relatively balanced between female participants comprising 51.5% and males 46.5%. Finally, most participants at the time of data collection were between 20 to 29 years of age (26.9%), married (42.4%) and employed full-time (52.1%).

4.2 Reliability

For this study, scale reliability was tested using Cronbach’s alpha coefficients, as they allowed the researcher to determine the internal consistency of the items used in the questionnaire and the extent to which these items were able to accurately measure their relevant constructs (Allen & Bennett, 2010; Field, 2018). As seen in Table 1, Cronbach’s alpha coefficient values for the measurement scales ranged between 0.801 to 0.931, which according to Babin and Zikmund (2016), is an indication that all the scales are highly reliable.

4.3 Assessing the measurement model and confirming construct validity

For the purposes of this study and in line with the selected ESEM approach, a number of fit indices were analysed, which include the χ^2 statistic, Root

Table 1: Reliability of the scales

Constructs	Cronbach’s alpha (α)
Disaffection	0.930
Disillusionment	0.923
Dissatisfaction	0.911
Alienation	0.801
Negative emotions	0.931
Customer detachment	0.867

Source: Author’s own research

Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) and Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR). The results of the analysis are listed in Table 2.

As seen in Table 2, all statistics with maximum cut-off values were well within the required estimates. This includes the chi-squared degrees of freedom (i.e., χ^2/df), which was below the recommended 5.0 cut-off with a value of 2.59 (Barrett, 2007; Pallant, 2016). Similarly, both the RMSEA and SRMR were below their maximum cut-off values of ≤ 0.1 and ≤ 0.08 with values of 0.054 and 0.017, respectively (Cho et al., 2020; Shi et al., 2019). Conversely, both the CFI and TLI, which required minimum values of above 0.95, were above their cut-off parameters with values of 0.991 and 0.987, respectively (Bagozzi & Yi, 2012; Bowen & Guo, 2011; Hooper et al., 2008; Hu & Bentler, 1999). Thus, as all values are within the recommended parameter values, the drivers of the detachment model can be said to have a good fit.

Incidentally, the confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) statistics listed in Table 2 above were included solely for comparison against the ESEM method and thereby validate the latter's use. Consequently, when comparing the statistics for the CFA and ESEM, it can be seen that not only do the 90% confidence intervals of both models not overlap, but in each instance, when compared, the statistical values provided by ESEM outperform that of the CFA, making ESEM the superior model. Additionally, during the data analysis period, it was discovered that the correlations assessed by the CFA model were very high; however, when tested with the ESEM model, the correlations were more acceptable, further supporting the superiority of the ESEM model.

4.4 Parameter estimates

After considering the goodness of fit statistics, parameter estimates of the ESEM analysis were used

to inspect the proposed driving factors of detachment: disaffection, disillusionment, dissatisfaction, alienation, and negative emotions, respectively. However, unlike traditional methods (e.g., CFA) that only report the factor loadings of items onto their own factor whilst forcibly maintaining all cross-loadings at zero, the ESEM approach also allows cross-loadings of facets to the other indicated factors (i.e., the ESEM analysis allows for the latent variables within the model to correlate with one another) (Booth & Hughes, 2014; Van Zyl & Klooster, 2022). When inspecting the target loadings of the items onto their respective factors, values of ≥ 0.50 are considered ideal, and values ranging between 0.30 to 0.50 are acceptable (i.e. the items adequately measure the latent factor they are associated with) (Alamer, 2022; Brace, Kemp, & Snelgar, 2009). According to Morin, Myers, and Lee (2020), cross-loading values closer to zero or at least lower than 0.3 are preferred; however, values between 0.30 and 0.50 can still be accepted. Values closer to zero are preferred for cross-loadings as it indicates that there are little to no similarities between the items measuring the other constructs included in the study (i.e., items measure their own latent construct only).

As seen in Table 3, all the proposed driving factors of detachment displayed acceptable significant targeted loadings and cross-loadings ranging from $\lambda = 0.31$ to $\lambda = 0.98$ and $\lambda = 0.00$ to $\lambda = 0.34$, respectively. The largest variation in factor loadings occurred for disillusionment (i.e., $\lambda = 0.31$ to $\lambda = 0.74$) and disaffection ($\lambda = 0.60$ to $\lambda = 0.98$). More moderate factor loadings were recorded for dissatisfaction ($\lambda = 0.48$ to $\lambda = 0.66$) and alienation ($\lambda = 0.31$ to $\lambda = 0.54$).

Regarding the cross-loadings, all factors were below the recommended cut-off value of ≤ 0.50 and were therefore deemed acceptable. Individually, the factor that the most items from disaffection cross-loaded significantly onto was alienation. Subse-

Table 2: Goodness of fit statistics

Model	χ^2	df	χ^2/df	CFI	TLI	RMSEA	90%CI	SRMR
CFA	997.673	309	3.23	0.985	0.983	0.064	[.060, .069]	0.026
ESEM	660.653	255	2.59	0.991	0.987	0.054	[.049, .060]	0.017

Source: Author's own research

Table 3: Factor and cross-loadings of the measurement items

Target Loading	Cross-Loadings			
Disaffection	Disillusionment	Dissatisfaction	Alienation	Negative Emotions
0.67**	0.13	-0.13*	0.04	0.09
0.82**	-0.09	-0.05	0.23**	-0.07
0.69**	0.34**	-0.15*	-0.19*	0.08
0.64**	0.25**	0.02	-0.29**	0.17
0.86**	-0.09	0.06	-0.20*	-0.03
0.60**	-0.01	0.17*	0.08	0.07
0.98**	-0.13**	0.02**	0.02**	-0.13**
0.62**	0.05	0.08	0.15*	0.08
0.82**	-0.15*	0.12	0.14*	-0.04
0.85**	-0.06	0.06	-0.07	-0.04
Disillusionment	Disaffection	Dissatisfaction	Alienation	Negative Emotions
0.55**	0.16**	0.22**	0.17**	-0.02
0.74**	0.13**	0.08**	0.10**	-0.01**
0.51**	0.06	0.22**	0.23**	0.08
0.31**	0.30**	0.19**	0.11*	0.11
Dissatisfaction	Disaffection	Disillusionment	Alienation	Negative Emotions
0.48**	0.18**	0.18**	0.18**	0.04
0.66**	0.08**	0.20**	0.02**	0.10**
0.48**	0.04	0.19**	-0.01	0.31**
Alienation	Disaffection	Disillusionment	Dissatisfaction	Negative Emotions
0.31**	0.00	0.14	0.07	0.20*
0.54**	0.10**	0.18**	0.00**	0.21**
0.45**	0.07	0.22**	0.07	0.24**
Negative Emotions	Disaffection	Disillusionment	Dissatisfaction	Alienation
0.89**	0.09	-0.19**	0.07	0.03
0.69**	0.02	0.01	0.22**	0.05
0.69**	0.05	0.09	-0.10*	0.21**
0.65**	0.12*	0.09	0.16*	-0.06
0.91**	-0.03**	-0.03**	-0.04**	0.10**

Source: Author's own research

Notes. Values presented in bold represent facets loading onto their own factors ([* = $p < 0.05$; ** = $p < 0.001$].)

quently, except for negative emotions, the items from disillusionment cross-loaded relatively well onto all the other factors, with dissatisfaction displaying the most significant results. Similarly, dissatisfaction's items cross-loaded relatively well onto all

the other items but loaded best onto disillusionment. Finally, the items from alienation cross-loaded best onto negative emotions, whilst the items from negative emotions cross-loaded most significantly onto dissatisfaction.

***Note:** the implication for items cross-loading well (i.e. < 0.30 and $p < 0.05$) is that the item in question effectively measures its own latent construct/factor and it is not a potential measure for any of the other constructs being measured. That is to say, each item(s) is a means of measure for its own latent construct only. See the discussion above for more details.

4.5 Correlation analysis

To ascertain the extent to which the six factors within the proposed detachment model correlate with one another, factor correlations were calculated. Table 4 illustrates the statistics for the correlation matrix for the latent variables.

As shown in Table 4, the correlation coefficients between the proposed detachment model factors,

i.e. disaffection (DA), disillusionment (DI), dissatisfaction (DS), alienation (AL), negative emotions (NE) and detachment (DE), were all significant ranging from medium ($r = 0.38$) to large effect sizes ($r = 0.88$).

4.6 Assessing the structural model

The results of the structural paths displayed in Table 5 indicate that all the hypotheses, except H4 ($p = 0.817$; H4 rejected), were supported. Specifically, disaffection ($\beta = 0.41$; $SE = 0.05$; $p < 0.001$), disillusionment ($\beta = 0.18$; $SE = 0.05$; $p < 0.001$), dissatisfaction ($\beta = 0.32$; $SE = 0.05$; $p < 0.001$) and negative emotions ($\beta = 0.15$; $SE = 0.06$; $p = 0.009$) were all positively and significantly related to customer detachment, thus supporting H1, H2, H3 and H5. A summary of the significant relationships identified by this study is presented in Figure 2.

Table 4: Correlation matrix of the latent variables

	DA	DI	DS	AL	NE	DE
DA	1.00					
DI	0.74**	1.00				
DS	0.70**	0.51**	1.00			
AL	0.54**	0.38*	0.57**	1.00		
NE	0.77**	0.71**	0.71**	0.68**	1.00	
DE	0.88**	0.75**	0.81**	0.58**	0.82**	1.00

Source: Author's own research

Notes. Medium effect size ($0.30 \leq r < 0.50$) **Large effect size ($r \geq 0.50$) (Cohen, 1988)

Table 5: Structural paths of the latent variables

	Path			β weight	SE	p-value	Result
H ₁	Disaffection	→	Detachment	0.41	0.05	0.001	Significant
H ₂	Disillusionment	→	Detachment	0.18	0.05	0.001	Significant
H ₃	Dissatisfaction	→	Detachment	0.32	0.05	0.001	Significant
H ₄	Alienation	→	Detachment	0.01	0.04	0.817	Not significant
H ₅	Negative emotions	→	Detachment	0.15	0.06	0.009	Significant

Source: Author's own research

Notes. β : standardised beta coefficient; SE: standard error; p-value: two-tailed statistical significance

Figure 2: Summary of significant relationships

Source: Author's own depiction

5 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Theoretical contributions

This study aimed to address the gap in detachment-related research within the field of marketing by empirically examining the possibility of detachment occurring within a customer-employee relationship setting and by providing a list of drivers that could lead to it. In order to achieve this goal, various literature studies pertaining to detachment were consulted and reliable scales for empirical testing were adapted from both the fields of psychology and marketing, which was analysed and interpreted. The interpreted results not only empirically confirmed the existence of detachment in customer-employee relationships but also confirmed that several of the drivers proposed by Eckardt and Spies (2023) were related to customer detachment.

The first of these proposed drivers, namely disaffection, proved to be statistically significantly related to customer detachment. This outcome offers

support to the notion put forth by Perrin-Martineq (2004) that in the process of becoming detached, customers will usually lose his/her previously held positive perceptions and affection for the relationship or offending attachment figure. Disillusionment, the second proposed driver, also proved to be statistically significantly related to customer detachment. This outcome reinforces the arguments of Evanschitzky et al. (2020) and Pervan and Martin (2012) that consistently failing to meet customer expectations will result in a de-idealised perception of the offending attachment figure, in turn, motivating the customer to detach as a means to cope with expected future disappointments. It should be noted that despite the respective arguments supporting the link between disaffection and disillusionment to customer detachment, neither of the proposed relationships has been empirically tested until now. Therefore, this paper empirically contributes to theory by confirming the link between disaffection and disillusionment, individually, towards customer detachment.

In terms of customer dissatisfaction and negative emotions, the results revealed that both these factors are statistically significantly related to customer detachment. These findings align with research presented by Ali et al. (2020), who found that customers' dissatisfaction could impact their detachment to their brand. Similarly, evidence provided by Lu et al. (2012) reveals that customers will often detach as a means of dealing with negative emotions and the circumstances that gave rise to them. Unlike the drivers discussed above, alienation did not prove to be statistically significantly related to customer detachment. An argument for this outcome could be that while a customer may feel a sense of exclusion or alienation in regard to a relationship with a particular attachment figure, it does not necessarily mean that they wish to detach themselves from it. Conversely, to resolve their feelings of alienation and exclusion, customers may actually desire to get closer to or strengthen his/her relationship with the offending attachment figure.

Considering the above discussion, this study provides new insight into the relationships between relationship disaffection, disillusionment, dissatisfaction, negative emotions, alienation, and detachment, which makes an original contribution to the body of knowledge in understanding customer detachment. This study also expands both the attachment and detachment domain as a model was developed and empirically tested to explain customer detachment in customer-employee relationships after reviewing and integrating theories from multidisciplinary literature. Moreover, this research has expanded the empirical understanding of the formation of detachment by confirming how disaffection, disillusionment, dissatisfaction, and negative emotions contribute to the eventual detachment of customers from employees or service providers.

This study can also be regarded as the first to link disaffection, disillusionment, dissatisfaction, and negative emotions to customer detachment in a customer-employee relationship setting. In so doing, it does not only support the attachment theory, but also clarifies the factors that contribute towards a detached customer.

5.2 Managerial implications

Taking the results discussed above into account, it is advised that in order to prevent the loss of successful and profitable long-term customer relationships, wealth managers should take strides to avoid detachment from occurring within their customer base, particularly, in regard to the effects of disaffection, disillusionment, dissatisfaction and negative emotions.

As disaffection occurs due to the cumulative effect of disappointments, dissatisfaction and unresolved conflicts (Abbasi & Alghamdi, 2017; Evanschitzky et al., 2020), wealth managers may wish to systematically review instances that have evoked negative reactions in their customers, with particular focus placed on recurring themes and instances that have remained unresolved for any extended period. Additional steps to combat disaffection can include the creation of a team dedicated not only to monitoring customer satisfaction levels but also taking actions to address any issues before they have the chance to escalate. Subsequently, disillusionment refers to being defeated in both expectation and hope (Maher et al., 2020), implying that the emotional state experienced by the disillusioned customers is a loss of faith in the wealth manager's ability to ever meet their needs. Therefore, to counteract customer disillusionment, wealth managers should strive to cultivate an image of being able to meet the needs of their customers and then consistently review if that image is being upheld. Moreover, wealth managers can also take steps to ensure that customers have realistic expectations regarding the management of their funds. For example, transparent communication that informs customers exactly what services can and cannot be realistically provided. This could include scheduling regular meetings with customers to ensure that their views and expectations continue to align with the services being offered.

Finally, while strategies to pre-empt any instances of customer dissatisfaction from occurring may not be feasible, wealth managers may instead opt to review the way in which they resolve negative emotions experienced by customers. An example of this could include training wealth management em-

employees to utilise pre-prepared strategies or protocols when dealing with specified customer grievances to prevent them from escalating. An additional strategy that may assist wealth managers in handling customer dissatisfaction includes regular training in conflict resolution and emotional intelligence. The techniques and insight provided by this form of training would enable wealth managers to better manage and mitigate negative emotions during customer interactions and thus prevent dissatisfaction from escalating before the situation can be resolved.

5.3 Limitations and recommendations for future research

The research findings discussed in this article are based on responses obtained from respondents in a single service setting (i.e., wealth management) using non-probability online convenience sampling. Thus, it is recommended that future research on this topic both uses probability sampling and strives to encompass additional service areas, as the current results cannot be generalised outside of their specified service setting.

Subsequently, while the constructs tested in this study assisted in both confirming the occurrence of detachment in customer-employee relationships and explaining its role therein, other equally important drivers of detachment identified by Eckardt & Spies (2023) were not included. Thus, future research on the topic could aim to examine the excluded drivers as possible antecedents customer detachment.

As noted above, the current study aimed to both explore the occurrence of detachment among wealth management customers and to test several potential drivers thereof. However, in adhering to these goals the study neglected to test the relationships between the drivers themselves thereby limiting a better understanding of detachment from being achieved. Consequently, it is recommended that future studies concerning the drivers of customer detachment assess not only the interconnections among them but also their sequential occurrence within the overall detachment process thereby highlighting their influence on the detachment phenomenon.

Similarly, while the current paper does contribute to the understanding of detachment and its causes in customer-employee relationships, other equally important variables that could have influenced the process may have been overlooked. For example, various demographic variables such as age, income and relationship status could be tested as potential moderators against the current and future hypothesised drivers of customer detachment.

During the course of this study, insight into the wealth management industry and the potential effects of detachment therein was predominantly obtained from limited existing literature. Consequently, additional external factors or related incidents outside of the wealth manager's control that could influence the detachment process such as market conditions, portfolio performance and even changes in customer preferences or needs could have been overlooked. To overcome this limitation, future studies on the topic should strive to obtain information pertaining to the industry and the potential drivers of detachment directly from wealth managers themselves through such means as interviews and/or focus groups.

Finally, extant literature suggests that detachment is not an instantaneous outcome but rather a process that occurs over time. Therefore, the results of this study which were obtained at a single point in time may not fully capture the dynamics of how customer detachment evolves. Therefore, future research could opt for a longitudinal approach to data collection and analysis allowing for a deeper understanding of detachment's temporal aspects to be achieved.

EXTENDED SUMMARY/IZVLEČEK

Uspešni in dobičkonosni odnosi med strankami in organizacijami so zakoreninjeni v vezeh, ki se med njimi oblikujejo. Navezanost stranke je dobro raziskana dimenzija teh odnosov, saj spodbuja zadovoljstvo strank, zaupanje, zavezanost, lojalnost in njihovo zadržanje. Vendar pa je enako pomemben koncept odtujenosti stranke, ki je opredeljena kot psihološka oddaljenost od figure navezanosti zaradi oslabiljenega odnosa, v kontekstu marketinga prejela omejeno pozornost. Negativne posledice odtujenosti na odnose narekujejo potrebo po njenem preučevanju v poslovnem kontekstu. Odtujenost, ki jo je prvotno opazil teoretik navezanosti Bowlby v odnosih med materjo in otrokom, je bila predvsem v psihologiji raziskana v različnih relacijskih kontekstih. Mladostniki se lahko odtujijo zaradi negativne družinske dinamike, medtem ko lahko odrasli doživljajo nenavezanost v nezadovoljivih romantičnih odnosih. V trženju je bila odtujenost preučevana predvsem v povezavi z odnosi stranka-blagovna znamka. Ta je pogosto sprožena z negativnimi dogodki, ki razočarajo stranke in s tem slabijo njihove čustvene vezi. Vendar pa odtujenost stranke v odnosih med stranko in zaposlenim ostaja neraziskana. Do nje lahko pride zaradi začetnih sprožilnih dogodkov, kot so napake pri storitvah ali izdelkih, kar vodi v nezadovoljstvo in negativna čustva. Kasnejši dvomi o zanesljivosti ali kompetentnosti figure navezanosti lahko povzročijo oddaljevanje in zmanjšano zanašanje nanjo, kar lahko privede do prekinitve odnosa.

Naslednji elementi predstavljajo možne dejavnike nenavezanosti:

Nezadovoljstvo v odnosih: Kopičenje razočaranj, nezadovoljstva in nerešenih konfliktov, ki povzročijo, da posamezniki izgubijo naklonjenost do odnosa, kar vodi v brezbržnost, apatijo in na koncu nenavezanost.

Razočaranje strank: Pojavi se, ko stranke večkrat doživljajo neizpolnjena pričakovanja, kar vodi do konca idealiziranega dojemanja figure navezanosti in s tem motivira odtujenost kot mehanizem spoprijemanja.

Nezadovoljstvo strank: Pogosto posledica napak pri izdelkih ali storitvah; nezadovoljstvo strank lahko vodi v odtujenost, saj lahko neizpolnjene potrebe spodbudijo posameznike, da se oddaljijo od vira svoje stiske.

Odtujevanje strank: Označuje pomanjkanje identifikacije z vrednotami in normami trga, kar lahko vodi do tega, da se stranke oddaljijo od institucij in odnosov, ki utelešajo te vrednote in norme.

Negativna čustva: Povzročena z dogodki, kot so napake pri storitvah; negativna čustva lahko vodijo v nenavezanost kot strategijo spoprijemanja, ki strankam omogoča, da se soočijo s stisko z oddaljevanjem od njenega vira.

Ta študija empirično potrjuje obstoj nenavezanosti strank v odnosih med strankami in zaposlenimi ter njeno povezavo z nezadovoljstvom, razočaranjem in negativnimi čustvi. Da bi preprečili odtujenost in ohranili dolgoročne odnose s strankami, bi morali nasloviti razočaranja, reševati konflikte, ohranjati pozitivno podobo in učinkovito upravljati z negativnimi čustvi. Prihodnje raziskave naj uporabijo verjetnostno vzorčenje in raziščejo dejavnike odtujenosti, ki v tej študiji niso bili obravnavani, da bi razširili naše razumevanje odtujenosti strank v različnih storitvenih kontekstih.

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